

CROPS

Curating, Replicating, Orchestrating, and Propagating Citizen Science across Europe

D1.2

Risk Management Plan

29 February 2024

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Glossary and Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The Risk Management Plan aims to allow project partners to see ahead potential risks and plan accordingly to reduce their negative impact. This document outlines procedures for identifying and handling uncommon causes of project deviations that may compromise objectives, i.e. risks. A Risk Assessment Tool has been created to support partners in the analysis and monitoring of potential risks.

This deliverable intends to:

- Provide all project partners a centralised location to identify the key risks in delivering the project and anticipate how each risk will be managed within the project.
- Create a risk reporting channel where each partner will have the opportunity to identify perceived and/or real risks.
- Present the mitigation plans for agreed risk to describe how the particular risk will be handled.

The Risk Management Plan will be updated and changed according to the evolution of procedures and progress during the lifetime of the project. The key goal of the risk management plan is to decrease the probability and impact of events adverse to the project. In contrast, any event that could have a positive impact should be exploited.

1 CROPS Risk Management

Risk management refers to all activities undertaken for identifying, analysing, monitoring, and controlling potential risks that could affect the execution of the project. In the proposal phase, the Consortium has identified the possible risks and critical issues that could negatively affect the overall quality or jeopardise the successful results of the CROPS project.

Aside from this preliminary assessment, accurate risk management will be a continuous process undertaken throughout the lifetime of the project. Additionally, risk management and mitigation measures will be applied to all tasks and activities which present a relevant level of criticality, and which therefore require a suitable approach to minimize risks to achieve the expected results.

1.1 Roles and Responsibilities

Figure 1 - Risk Management: Responsibility Flow

Task Leaders and Work Package Leaders are the first line risk monitors. They have the responsibility for continuously monitoring work progress and delivery of the Tasks and Work Packages. In this context, they assure the identification and management of the risks, and they should inform the Risk manager. If new risks are identified, they should be reported to the Risk Manager who will update the Risk Assessment Tool (Section 1.2.1).

Risk Manager – INOVA+ – is responsible for coordinating the risks management actions with the Consortium members, and the **PMP**. In case of major risks/ deviations, the Risk Manager shall activate the **General Assembly** who will decide on the matters as listed in section 6.3.7 of the Consortium Agreement.

1.2 Tools

1.2.1 Risk Assessment Tool

As introduced in *Deliverable 1.1 Project Management Plan*, a CROPS Tracking Tool was developed. A dedicated tab was created to provide support to partners in the analysis and monitoring of potential risks. This tab translates the CROPS **Risk Assessment Tool**, containing (i) a breakdown of the risks identified; (ii) a section to list new risks; (iii) and a section to assess the impact of the risk on the project implementation and agree on measures to be taken.

An overview of the tool can be consulted in Figure 2.

1.2.2 Dedicated meetings

To guarantee proper analysis and discussion on potential risks, a risk analysis will be performed:

- Regularly, at least every 4 months, during Consortium Meetings previewed. Risk Manager (INOVA+) will coordinate the analysis and discussion among partners.
- Extraordinarily, in case a risk is identified to occur. Work Package Leaders shall inform the Risk Manager (INOVA+) and a dedicated extraordinary meeting shall be scheduled. If a consortium meeting is close, the meeting shall be programmed during the consortium regular meetings.

1.2.3 List of identified risks and mitigation measures

Table 1 provides the list of identified risks. It captures the essential information about each identified risk, including its nature, potential impact, the likelihood of occurrence, and the proposed actions or mitigation measures to address it. By presenting this information in a structured and accessible format, the risk management table enables CROPS partners to have a comprehensive overview of the project's risk landscape and make informed decisions regarding risk response and allocation of resources.

Table 1 - CROPS Potential Risks and Mitigation Measures

Description of risk	Likelihood & Severity	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Implementation difficulties due to personnel changes at partner organisations	L: low S: high	ALL WPs	Flexibility in added resources or making use of other partner expertise; engaging external specialists.
Lack of internal resources to complete all tasks as planned	L: low S: medium	ALL WPs	Target effort on areas with the highest potential of success. Planning for cross partnership support allows other partners to support the activity or event.
Opt-out of a consortium member	L: low S: high	WP1	The likelihood will be kept low through continuous consultation, high-frequency communication, and clear conflict-resolution procedures. If one of the partners is forced to withdraw, the consortium will invite suitable members from industry or academia to replace the missing party, thus minimising the negative impact.

Failure to produce deliverables on time or to sufficient quality	L: low S: high	WP1	The project management plan (D1.1) will set out a rigorous framework for delivery, including internal peer review. Reports and key outputs will be developed in stages so that basic functionality is reached relatively early, and a lack of progress can be detected.
Financial divergences	L: low S: medium	WP1	Potential excess of the estimated budget might occur. The consortium and mainly the coordinator will review the budget issues throughout the project duration very carefully and monitor costs closely to anticipate potential excess on time and suggest responsive action.
Impossibility/ unavailability of JRC for actively participating in the assessment workshop	L: medium S: low	WP2	The AB has been structured to include experts from each of the 5 EU missions. These can and will be leveraged to invite domain experts to the respective mission-specific workshops. The overall positioning of the consortium also ensures high outreach among these disciplines and communities.
Difficulties in assuring the adequate participation of stakeholders	L: low S: high	WP3, WP4, WP5	Partners have extensive networks of contacts that will be mobilized since the beginning of the project to assure awareness and adherence to the project activities, such as surveys, interviews, and mutual learning workshops.
Collaboration with other EU projects and initiatives is not mutually beneficial or not effective and efficient	L: low S: medium	ALL WPs	CROPS will plan early the engagement and possible bridges with the selected EU projects and initiatives by identifying mutual interests and cooperation areas. Meetings will be set with the coordinators of the other actions for stimulating common understanding on objectives and collaboration areas.
Epidemics or other crises affecting international engagement and activities	L: low S: medium	ALL WPs	Many meetings and most project support provided are planned to be online. If restrictions hinder in-person meetings and workshop activities, the consortium will review the project plan and put more effort into communication and online support.

Description of risk	Likelihood (L) & severity (S) (low, medium, high)	WP	1st line Monitoring Responsible	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	CONSORTIUM MEETING - RISK CHECKPOINT 1			CONSORTIUM MEETING - RISK CHECKPOINT 1				
					Risk Impacting the Project?			If critical risk, identify concrete mitigation measures and who will execute them	Risk Impacting the Project?			If critical risk, identify concrete mitigation measures and who will execute them
					Likelihood	Severity	Obs.		Likelihood	Severity	Obs.	
Implementation difficulties due to personnel changes at partner organisations	L: low S: high	WP1	INOVA+	Flexibility in added resources or making use of other partner expertise; engaging external specialists.	Low	High			Low	High		
		WP2	IFC									
		WP3	IIASA									
		WP4	INOVA+									
		WP5	Outbe									
		WP6	EarthWatch									
Lack of internal resources to complete all tasks as planned	L: low S: medium	WP1	INOVA+	Target effort on areas with the highest potential of success. Planning for cross partnership support allows other partners to support the activity or event.	Low	Medium			Low	Medium		
		WP2	IFC									
		WP3	IIASA									
		WP4	INOVA+									
		WP5	Outbe									
		WP6	EarthWatch									
Opt-out of a consortium member	L: low S: high	WP1	INOVA+	The likelihood will be kept low through continuous consultation, high-frequency communication, and clear conflict-resolution procedures. If one of the partners is forced to withdraw, the consortium will invite suitable members from industry or academia to replace the missing party, thus minimising the negative impact.								
Failure to produce deliverables on time or to sufficient quality	L: low S: high	WP1	INOVA+	The project plan (D1.1) will set out a rigorous framework for delivery, including internal peer review. Reports and key outputs will be developed in stages so that basic functionality is reached relatively early, and a lack of progress can be detected.								
Financial divergences	L: low S: medium	WP1	INOVA+	Potential excess of the estimated budget might occur. The consortium and mainly the coordinator will review the budget issues throughout the project duration very carefully and monitor costs closely to anticipate potential excess on time and suggest responsive action.								
Impossibility/unavailability of JRC for actively participating in the assessment workshop	L: medium S: low	WP2	IFC	The AB has been structured to include experts from each of the 5 EU missions. These can and will be leveraged to invite domain experts to the respective mission-specific workshops. The overall positioning of the consortium also ensures high outreach among these disciplines and communities.								
Difficulties in assuring the adequate participation of stakeholders	L: low S: high	WP3	IIASA	Partners have extensive networks or contacts that will be mobilized since the beginning of the project to assure awareness and adherence to the project activities, such as surveys, interviews, and mutual learning workshops.								
		WP4	INOVA+									
		WP5	Outbe									
Collaboration with other EU projects and initiatives is not mutually beneficial or not effective and efficient	L: low S: medium	WP1	INOVA+	CROPS will plan early the engagement and possible bridges with the selected EU projects and initiatives by identifying mutual interests and cooperation areas. Meetings will be set with the coordinators of the other actions for stimulating common understanding on objectives and collaboration areas.								
		WP2	IFC									
		WP3	IIASA									
		WP4	INOVA+									
		WP5	Outbe									
		WP6	EarthWatch									
Epidemics or other crises affecting international engagement and activities	L: low S: medium	WP1	INOVA+	Many meetings and most project support provided are planned to be online. If restrictions hinder in-person meetings and workshop activities, the consortium will review the project plan and put more effort into communication and online support.								
		WP2	IFC									
		WP3	IIASA									
		WP4	INOVA+									
		WP5	Outbe									
		WP6	EarthWatch									
Other Risks identified? If yes, please describe												
Description of risk	Likelihood (L) & severity (S) (low, medium, high)	WP	1st line Monitoring Responsible	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	CONSORTIUM MEETING - RISK CHECKPOINT 1			CONSORTIUM MEETING - RISK CHECKPOINT 1				
					Risk Impacting the Project?			If critical risk, identify concrete mitigation measures and who will execute them	Risk Impacting the Project?			If critical risk, identify concrete mitigation measures and who will execute them
					Likelihood	Severity	Obs.		Likelihood	Severity	Obs.	
New risk 1 ...		WP...			Low	High			Low	High		

Figure 2 - Risk Assessment Tool

2 CROPS Risk Management Action Plan: step-by-step

CROPS Risk Management Plan involves different steps to support partners in effectively navigate uncertainties and increase the likelihood of the project success.

Figure 3 provides a schematic representation of the CROPS risk management process.

Figure 3 - CROPS risk management process

2.1 Step 1. Risk Identification

Throughout the lifetime of the CROPS project, partners will be encouraged to identify, describe and communicate (via email, MSTeams or during meetings) any potential risk. As mentioned previously, Task Leaders and Work Package Leaders, as first line work progress monitors, are encouraged to share any potential risks with the Risk Manager, who will activate the necessary actions to discuss the risk.

The following issues shall be considered as tools and techniques for risk identification:

- Analysis of deliverable status;
- Analysis of WP schedules and scopes;
- Regular communication between Task Leaders, WP leaders and Risk Manager.

2.2 Step 2. Risk exposure analysis

If a risk is identified, partners shall analyse them during dedicated meetings (*Section 1.2.2*). Risk Manager will coordinate the discussion and register analysis in the Risk Assessment Tool (*Section 1.2.1*).

Risks will be analysed considering the Risk Matrix in Figure 4, which estimates the risk exposure based on two main aspects:

- (i) Level of likelihood to occur (low/medium/high). The likelihood is the estimated probability that the risk will materialise even after taking account of the mitigating measures put in place.
- (ii) Level of severity (low/medium/high). The relative seriousness of the risk and the significance of its effect, i.e. impact on the project objectives and activities.

Figure 4 - Risk Matrix

2.3 Step 3. Closure or Definition of mitigation measures

If the risk identified is not assessed as critical, i.e. if Likelihood and Severity are considered low, the risk assessment process shall close. However, partners shall continuously monitor the probability of that risk occur.

If a critical risk is plausible to occur, i.e. if an event or issue have high probability to occur and could have a high adverse impact on the ability of the project to achieve its objectives, partners shall define concrete mitigation measures and who will execute them.

The assigned partner is responsible for executing the risk mitigation activities and to report results (both positive and negative) to the other consortium partners.

If a mitigation action cannot be effectively carried out or does not solve the risk, other mitigation measures shall be defined in dedicated meetings.

3 Conclusion

D1.2 Risk Management Plan serves as a comprehensive framework for identifying, assessing and mitigating the risks within CROPS project. By adopting a proactive approach to risk management, the project partners showcase their proactive approach and readiness to safeguard and achieve the project objectives.